

MARINEWIND

Market Uptake Measures of Floating Offshore Wind Technology Systems (FOWTs)

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T1.3_Greek Lab 2nd Co-creation Workshop Report

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1 EVENT DETAILS

EVENT LOCATION: Thessaloniki International Exhibition & Congress Centre, 154 Egnatias Street, 54636, Thessaloniki, Greece.

EVENT DATE: Friday, 08 March 2024 (Duration: 2 hours)

EVENT TITLE: Co-creation Workshop on Offshore Wind Energy in Greece: Challenges and Opportunities for Sustainable Development

TYPE OF EVENT: Physical

CATEGORY OF THE EVENT: Co-creation Workshop

EVENT AFFILIATION: Renewable EnergyTech

LEAD ORGANISER: Q-PLAN International

LANGUAGE: Greek

CONCEPT:

The MARINEWIND 2nd co-creation workshop aimed to bring together different Greek and international stakeholders interested in the developments of Offshore wind in Greece, in order to discuss and explore the potential of the Floating Offshore Wind Technologies (FOWTs) in Greece. The workshop was organised at the Renewable EnergyTech expo in Thessaloniki. The targeted exhibition was a great opportunity to gather great audience from all the different key stakeholders, including highly recognized academic and industrial stakeholders, to discuss the recent developments on the (floating) Offshore Wind Market in Greece and foster potential synergies for the development of OWFs in the upcoming period, thus resulting in a more sustainable development of the offshore wind sector.

More specifically, the workshop aimed to inform the participants about the MARINEWIND project, the landscape of Offshore Wind Technologies in Greece, explore the significant issues of spatial planning and identify the most critical barriers and enablers for the investment on FOWTs in Greece through a co-creation session. The participants were actively participated in the co-creation session, sharing their knowledge and expertise, and expressed their views on what is needed in order to accelerate the commercialisation and deployment of FOWTs in Greece.

OBJECTIVES

- Increase awareness on FOWTs via co-creation activities that directly engage policy and decision makers, market and business actors, civil society organisations and funding bodies.
- Identify critical barriers and enablers on FOWTs in order to accelerate the investment and commercialization these technologies.
- Increase Social acceptance on FOWTs facilities and installations by directly involving local communities and citizens and by addressing potential environmental issues.
- Facilitate communication and collaboration among all the stakeholders directly and indirectly involved in Greek MARINEWIND Lab.

TARGET AUDIENCE:

Due to the fact that in the 1st MARINEWIND co-creation workshop in Greece the participants were mainly industrial stakeholders, the 2nd co-creation workshop targeted mainly representatives from academia, but also having the strong presence of industrial stakeholders, public authorities, civil society and green innovators, directly or indirectly involved in the Greek Lab. For each specific category, the involved actors were:

- **Industry:** FOWT installation developers, engineering companies, tech/project developers, trade associations (fisheries and tourism).
- **Academia:** Scientific & Research Community.
- **Public authorities:** National Regulatory authority for energy, policymakers.
- **Civil society:** NGOs, civil society organisations, and citizens.
- **Green innovation:** SMEs, insurers/law firms, ecologists, environmental organisations.

PARTICIPANTS OF YOUR EVENT: 45 participants

Figure 1: Participants overview

2 OVERVIEW OF CONTRIBUTIONS AND INTERVENTIONS BY THE SPEAKERS

The 2nd MARINEWIND co-creation workshop kicked-off with a brief presentation of the project objectives and activities, by the Project Manager of Q-PLAN International, Leonidas Parodos. The project overview was followed by five speeches, covering various aspects of the Offshore Wind Energy and Technologies in Greece, focusing on FOWT, as depicted in the following sub-sections. The co-creation workshop concluded with the presentation of MARINEWIND's next steps, as well as the brief overview of the WENDY's objectives and Knowledge Exchange Platform, which is another Horizon Europe project about wind energy.

2.1 The development of Offshore Wind potential – Regulatory framework

The opening speech started with a comprehensive overview of Greece's objectives in respect of energy transition and Offshore Wind Technologies (OWT), the existing regulatory framework, the responsible authorities and procedural mechanisms, as well as the compelling benefits associated with the development of OWT in the country, by the Associate Professor and Member of the Plenary Board of Regulatory Authority for Energy Waste and Water (RAEWW) in Greece, Dr. Komninos G. Komnios.

He began by discussing Greece's overarching objectives in transitioning towards green energy, emphasizing the nation's commitment to reducing reliance on fossil fuels and embracing renewable energy sources as part of its sustainability agenda.

Dr. Komnios then turned to the new regulatory framework governing OWT in Greece. He presented the recent legislative developments aimed at facilitating the development and deployment of offshore wind projects, also highlighting the integration into them of the principles of environmental protection and sustainable energy.

Moreover, Dr. Komnios elaborated on the roles and responsibilities of the various regulatory bodies and authorities tasked with overseeing offshore wind energy initiatives in Greece, emphasizing on their crucial role in the licensing and granting procedure.

Another significant aspect of his speech was the procedural stages involved in obtaining licenses for offshore wind projects and the competitive process for selecting investors and developers. Dr. Komnios provided details into the complex regulatory procedures and the rigorous selection criteria for investing in Greece's offshore wind sector.

Finally, Dr. Komnios outlined the economic benefits associated with developing OWT in Greece, which ranged from the creation of high-expertise jobs to local and national industrial growth.

2.2 Opportunities and Challenges of the Offshore Wind market in Greece

The next speech focused on the key characteristics and attributes of the Offshore Wind in Greece, by the CEO of FARIA Renewables, Thalia Valkouma, highlighting the most crucial of them as depicted below:

- Excellent wind resource heights located mainly in the Aegean Sea far from mainland.
- There are areas suitable for both bottom fixed and floating projects.
- The estimated technical potential for bottom fixed projects is 8 GW minimum, while for floating projects is approximately 40 GW.

Figure 2: Wind speed

Figure 3: Geopolitical conditions

Figure 4: Steep seabed with deep water close to coast

In addition, the challenges, opportunities and perspectives for deploying OWTs in Greece were briefly presented, and the most critical defined for the offshore wind in Greece are summarised in Table 1 and Table 2.

Table 1: Offshore wind challenges in Greece

Technical Challenges	Regulatory Challenges	Commercial Challenges
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Scale up quickly to industrial size projects ○ Steep learning curve for bottom fixed projects and ride the global floating wind wave ○ Unexplored seabed compared to other markets ○ Infrastructure challenge (grid, ports) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Stable OW specific legal framework ○ Compatibility with national Marine Spatial Planning ○ Clearly communicated long term OW installation targets ○ Permitting framework to be tailored to OW individualities and timelines to be rationalised 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ FDI and project management experience required ○ Lack of experience in the local banking sector ○ Specific strategy per technology ○ Formation of Mega Consortiums

Table 2: Offshore wind opportunities and perspectives in Greece

Opportunities	Perspectives
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Creation of jobs ○ Repatriate highly qualified personnel ○ Export products to other markets ○ Creation of national and international energy hubs ○ Integration of local supply chain in the OW projects 	<p>Developers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Key offshore wind market with a pipeline of projects ● Potential Mediterranean energy hub for energy activities <p>National</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● OW to become the largest renewables technology in the energy mix ● Meet decarbonization targets

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Leverage on Greek maritime industry experience on OW supply chain 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase energy security and independence from fossil fuel imports <p>Supply Chain</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Attract investments, diversify product offering and lead innovative technology
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2.3 Issues of siting Renewable Energy Sources (RES) in the Maritime space

Following the opportunities and challenges of the Offshore Wind market in Greece, Dr. Dimitra Vagiona, professor of the Department of Spatial Planning and Development Engineering in the Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (AUTH), introduced the issues raised when exploring potential locations in the Maritime space to site RES, such Offshore Wind Technologies and Photovoltaics.

Specifically, Dr. Vagiona referred to the restrictions for the siting of Offshore Wind farms, in terms of the institutional framework. Furthermore, she analyzed both the criteria for excluding an area as a candidate for Offshore Wind farm development, as well as the evaluation criteria for the eligible areas. In addition, Dr. Vagiona presented the tools and techniques that are used to collect the necessary data of a potential for siting area and to exclude or/and evaluate the respective area.

2.4 Offshore Wind potential - The Greek specialty

The next speech focused on the methodology and tools to estimate the Wind potential in Greek areas for optimized Wind Turbine siting and energy efficiency, by Dimitrios Fousekis, Wind & SCADA specialist at FloatMast.

Specifically, Mr. Fousekis presented the methodology for illustrating the attributes of Wind Potential (e.g., wind speed and directions), along with the necessary data to be collected, the tools and methods (CFD, ZephyTools, OpenFOAM) to be used for the calculations as well as the factors (e.g., aerodynamic roughness) to be considered for the calculations. An example depicting the Directional frequencies of different Wind velocities for several areas in Greece is presented below:

Figure 5: Directional frequencies by Wind Speed Range (%)

Finally, the results of these calculations have shown that there are 3 peculiarities for the Greek Maritime space:

- Proximity of OWT to coasts with significant relief.
- The airflow has 1-2 main directions.
- There are marine plots in Greece with significant velocity & turbulence inhomogeneities.

Based on the above specificities to the Greek maritime space, it was highlighted that there are increased requirements for accurate measurements of speed, wind direction and wind turbulence to ensure a proper citation of the offshore wind turbines.

2.5 Technologies and Challenges of FOWT

The final speech focused on the factors that make FOWT development both possible and beneficial, the various existing FOWT technologies across Europe along with the advantages of each technology, but also the existing requirements and challenges for the development of such projects. Dr. Eva Loukogeorgaki, Professor of the Marine Constructions at the Department of Civil Engineering in AUTH, was responsible for the presentation, providing fruitful insights and knowledge to the participants.

Dr. Loukogeorgaki started by analysing the main drivers for developing FOWT projects. Particularly, the possibility of access for the exploitation of offshore wind energy in areas of great depth, the existence of constant and strong winds in the Greek maritime space, along with the technological development

of the wind energy domain can play a crucial role in ensuring access to affordable, reliable and sustainable energy as well as in paving the way for a climate neutral future.

Consequently, Dr. Loukogeorgaki presented the main categories of FOWTs, based on their foundation, as well as a few existing technologies, highlighting their benefits. There are four basic foundations for FOWTs which are presented below:

- 1) Barge
- 2) Semi-Submersible
- 3) Spar
- 4) Tension-Leg Platform (TLP)

Figure 6: Basic Categorisation of FOWTs

Finally, Dr. Loukogeorgaki presented the technological, administrative and other challenges and requirements for developing FOWTs, which are included in the table below.

Technological	Administrative + Other
Float design with sufficient resistance & dynamic behavior with "scaling-up" possibility	Need for significant investment & upgrading of facilities
Simplicity of float design	Improved Operation & Maintenance methods and standardization
Modular float design	Upgrading existing and/or forming new port infrastructures
Adaptability in float design	Development of local supply chain & domestic human resources
Use of float construction materials available in different countries/installation areas	Need for specialized equipment and upgrading the existing electrical network
Construction materials suitable for different local environmental conditions	Development and adoption of regulations/standards for the FOWTs life cycle
Adoption of innovative design & material/component practices to reduce cost, risk & increase safety	Improved installation methods and equipment (e.g. self-assembly & semi-submersible vessels) and standardization

3 CO-CREATION ACTIVITIES

One of the main activities of the event was the co-creation session in order to interact with the audience. For that reason, a survey on the MENTIMETER online tool was prepared by APRE, adapted and translated by Q-PLAN and shared to the participants (in Greek) in order to collect useful information. It is common in such co-creation activities that some of the event participants didn't join the online tool.

The official results in Greek language along with the number of individual responses, as drawn from the MENTIMETER Tool, are presented in Annex I.

3.1 Question 1: Types of organisations represented

The attendees participated in the co-creation activities were mostly Business oriented, covering a variety of technology providers, engineering companies and offshore wind project developers. In addition, there was adequate participation from research and academia representatives, green innovation stakeholders, public authorities and civil society actors. Finally, only one (1) participant chose the "other" option meaning that he categorizes himself in a different category. In total, 18 participants were actively engaged in the co-creation activities as indicated in Figure 7.

Figure 7: Type of organisations involved

3.2 Question 2: Key enabling factors to invest in FOWTs

For this question, the participants were asked to select up to three options from the provided list about the key enabling factors to invest in FOWTs, in Greece. Based on their responses, the most critical enabling factor was the Technological maturity, followed by the clear Regulatory framework. Very close in total responses was the need for a Stable national transmission grid, as well as the potential for development of the local supply chain. The remaining options seem to be less significant, at least in the initial development phase of the offshore wind sector in Greece.

Figure 8: Key enabling factors to invest in FOWTs

3.3 Question 3: Most significant risk in the supply chain

Concerning the risks associated with the supply chain, the participants highlighted as most significant, by far, the lack of adequate infrastructure which reflects the fact that there is a great need for developing adequate port infrastructure to deal with the offshore wind turbines in Greece. The next concern of the participants was the limited capacity of the supply chain at the local level, identifying potential difficulties in adapting to increased capacities from the local suppliers. All responses are summarized in Figure 9.

Figure 9: Significant risks in Supply Chain for floating offshore wind

3.4 Question 4: Engagement of industry with local communities and other stakeholders to address concerns related to the deployment of floating offshore wind projects

The next question was searching for ways in which the industry can better engage and work with local communities and interested stakeholders with the aim of addressing concerns about FOWT’s development. The most popular response was the implementation of community outreach and educational programmes, followed by informing local communities about the financial benefits of FOWTs, and the proposition of biodiversity recovery plans, environmental benefits and safety measures. In addition, the promotion of inclusive decision-making was very close to participants’ preferences, while the rest responses seemed, according to the votes, to be less effective.

Figure 10: Ways of engagement of industry with local communities and other stakeholders to address concerns related to the deployment of FOWT projects

3.5 Question 5: Key environmental concerns associated with floating offshore wind

The following question concerned the identification of key environmental concerns that are associated with FOWTs. Most of the participants highlighted that the Impact on marine ecosystems along with Habitat degradation are the most crucial concerns related to FOWTs. Important environmental concerns were also considered the Hydrodynamic changes, as well as the visual impact, noise, electromagnetic fields that might be created and the heat pollution. All the responses can be found sorted in Figure 11.

Figure 11: Key environmental concerns related to FOWTs

3.6 Question 6: Challenges that need to be addressed to support the growth of the floating offshore wind industry

This question was looking for identifying the most important infrastructure challenges that impede the development of the floating offshore wind industry. The participants were asked to vote for up to 3 choices. According to the results, investment in port facilities (logistics, installation and maintenance phase) is considered as the most important challenge, followed by the need to enhance grid connectivity and transmission infrastructure. Participants seemed to have had mixed opinions regarding the scalability of current solutions to commercial scale, the technological maturity, and the investment in adequate port infrastructures for the testing phase. Finally, the rest options are not considered, according to participants, challenging issues to be addressed.

Figure 12: Challenges impeding the development of the floating offshore wind industry

3.7 Question 7: Strategies to build trust and acceptance among communities where FOWTs are being deployed

Regarding the increase of trust and acceptance among communities where FOWTs are being deployed, participants were asked to estimate which strategies could help towards this direction. Selecting up to 3 choices, the most impactful strategy according to the results was to foster public participation through community engagement programmes, workshops, inclusive decision-making etc. In this question we had balanced options among participants as it is depicted in Figure 13, while adopting strategies such as defining of fishing areas/zones and minimizing sea use and co-existing conflicts seemed to have no meaningful impact on building trust and acceptance among communities.

Figure 13: Strategies to build trust and acceptance among communities

3.8 Question 8: Activities in conflict with the offshore wind sector

In the final question, the participants responded on which activity is most in conflict with the offshore wind sector and they had to rank all the potential answers according to their beliefs. The sector that was selected as the most in conflict with the offshore wind sector in Greece was the environmental protection, closely followed by the fishing and tourism sector. In the 4th position, the respondents ranked the shipping sector slightly behind in their preferences. The participants that selected the “other” option believe that none of the activities are in conflict with the offshore wind sector.

Figure 14: Activities in conflict with the offshore wind sector in Greece

4 SUMMARY OF IDENTIFIED BARRIERS AND ENABLERS

The 2nd of the three co-creation workshops for T1.3 with regards to the Greek Lab has been mainly dedicated to barriers perceived by the stakeholders for the investment on FOWTs, and to potential enablers, as it did the 1st co-creation workshop. This time, specific focus was given to the academic and scientific community which shared their research and experiences from the offshore wind developments in Greece. Thanks to the data collected, the next workshop will then focus on solutions and policies to ease the installation of Offshore Wind Parks. The table below summarises the main barriers, criticalities and bottlenecks identified during the workshop on one side, and the most significant enablers and incentives on the other. Several of them have been already detected during the 1st CCW, thus validating our previous results.

BARRIERS	ENABLERS
<p>Lack of infrastructure The inadequate infrastructure, such as ports and grid, is a significant criticality according to participants, due to the fact that it increases the risk in the supply chain for floating offshore wind and prevents the smooth development of FOWT projects.</p>	<p>Technological maturity The technological maturity of platforms and dynamic cables in Greece is considered as key enabler factor by participants, to invest in FOWT projects in Greece.</p>
<p>Environmental impact The environmental impact on of developing FOWT projects, particularly the impact on marine ecosystems, can result in significant delays and costs (e.g., further environmental impact studies), preventing potential investors to invest in FOWTs in Greece.</p>	<p>Process clarity Significant effort of the Greek state to establish a clear permitting process in place, which is administered by competent and trusted entities (HEREMA, Ministries, etc.).</p>
<p>Regulatory framework stability The different responsible public bodies (Ministries, HEREMA, Independent Power Transmission Operator (IPTO), and the Regulatory Authority for Energy (RAE)) for granting FOWT permits, along with the incomplete regulatory framework may cause significant bureaucracy and discourage potential investors.</p>	<p>Greek offshore wind potential Greece has an extremely high offshore wind potential, thanks to the climate and the geographical position it holds on the energy map of Europe (e.g., stable winds, high intensity winds, etc.). The high wind potential has higher efficiency and profit derived from the offshore wind parks, thus attracting more investors.</p>
<p>Greek Commercial Banking The insufficient experience in the local banking sector results in lack of financing tools and supplementary facilities that could be used by the investor to mitigate risks across the supply chain.</p>	<p>Greek peculiarities The relief of the Greek maritime space has several areas with ideal depths for developing FOWTs, as well as the estimated technical potential for floating projects (40GW) is far greater than bottom fixed (8GW).</p>
<p>Lack of integrated Maritime Spatial Planning The lack of an integrated Maritime Spatial Planning in Greece is highlighted as a barrier on potential investments on offshore wind projects in Greece.</p>	<p>International cooperations between companies Collaborative projects involving Greek and international firms with substantial expertise in developing and managing offshore wind initiatives.</p>

<p>Social acceptance of the Offshore Wind Farms</p> <p>There is widespread resistance to the advancement of wind energy, both onshore and offshore, in Greece. This resistance has the potential to lead to considerable delays in the permitting and construction phase, thereby jeopardizing the economic feasibility of the projects.</p>	<p>Policy support</p> <p>Substantial economic incentives and local-level advantages can serve as catalysts for investments in FOWTs.</p>
<p>Limitations in local supply chain</p> <p>To ensure the successful deployment of offshore wind projects in Greece, substantial improvements are necessary in the local supply chain, which currently faces significant limitations across nearly all critical supply chain activities.</p>	

5 ANNEX I – MENTIMETER TOOL RESULTS

Ποια απο τις παρακατω κατηγοριες σας αντιπροσωπευει καλυτερα;

Ποιοι είναι οι πιο σημαντικοί παράγοντες που επιτρέπουν την επένδυση σε Πλωτές Υπερακτίες Αιολικές Τεχνολογίες (ΠΥΑΤ); (εώς 3 επιλογές)

Ποιο είναι το πιο σημαντικό ρίσκο για την αλυσίδα εφοδιασμού;

Πώς συνεργάζεται ο κλάδος με τις τοπικές κοινότητες και τα ενδιαφερόμενα μέρη για να αντιμετωπίσει τις ανησυχίες σχετικά με την ανάπτυξη των ΠΥΑΤ;

Ποιες είναι οι βασικές περιβαλλοντικές ανησυχίες που σχετίζονται με τις ΠΥΑΤ; Ιεράρχηση των επιλογών

Ποιες προκλήσεις πρέπει να αντιμετωπιστούν για να υποστηριχθεί ή αναπτυχθεί η πλωτή υπερακτία αιολικής βιομηχανίας; (εώς 3 επιλογές)

Ποιες στρατηγικές μπορούν να χρησιμοποιηθούν για οικοδόμηση εμπιστοσύνης & αποδοχής μεταξύ των κοινοτήτων όπου αναπτύσσονται οι ΠΥΑΤ; (εώς 3 επιλογές)

Ποια δραστηριότητα είναι σε μεγαλύτερη σύγκρουση με τον τομέα της υπερακτίας αιολικής ενέργειας; Ιεράρχηση δραστηριοτήτων

